

CIVIL LAW PROCEDURE FOR COMPENSATION OF DAMAGES CAUSED BY AN ADMINISTRATIVE OFFENSE

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Abstract: The article analyzes the concept of damages caused as a result of an administrative offense and describes the civil law procedure for their compensation.

Keywords: administrative offense, damages caused as a result of an administrative offense, methods and procedure for compensation.

In accordance with Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state provides victims with protection and access to justice, and creates conditions for compensation of damages inflicted upon them.[1] According to Article 985 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, damages caused to the person or property of a citizen by unlawful action (inaction), as well as damages caused to a legal entity, including lost profits, must be fully compensated by the person who caused the damages. According to Article 38 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility, a person who has committed an administrative offense is obliged to compensate for the damages caused as a result of the administrative offense.[2] Based on the foregoing, it can be said that our national legislation provides for the legal basis for compensation of damages caused as a result of an administrative offense.

Compensation for property and moral damage caused as a result of an administrative offense, that is, the restoration of violated rights and freedoms of persons affected by the offense, acts as a protective function of administrative responsibility. In this case, unlike administrative liability, civil liability is not punitive for the offender, but compensatory, aimed at restoring the violated rights of the victim. After all, regardless of whether an administrative penalty is applied to the offender, he is obliged to compensate for the damage caused as a result of the administrative offense. That is, the application of an administrative penalty to the offender does not release him from compensation for the damage caused as a result of the administrative offense.

The Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility establishes the following 3 procedures for compensation for property damage caused as a result of an administrative offense:

firstly, the body (official) authorized to consider cases of administrative offenses has the right to decide on compensation for property damage, if it does

not exceed the amount of the established basic calculated value at the time of application of the penalty;

Secondly, the court in criminal cases considers the issue of compensation for damage regardless of the amount of property damage caused;

Thirdly, compensation for property damage caused as a result of an administrative offense is resolved in a civil law manner.

It was noted that our national legislation provides that compensation for damage caused as a result of committing administrative offenses can be resolved not only in the administrative-legal procedure, but also in the civil-legal procedure. Professor N. Imomov states that..."each branch of law uses its own methods and means in combating offenses and makes its worthy contribution to this process"[3], while Professor O. Okyulov emphasizes that "recognizing civil-legal protection of human rights and interests as a comprehensive, large-scale, and accessible method, criminal-legal and administrative-legal protection is effective and effective"[4]. Certainly, resolving the issue of damage caused as a result of an administrative offense in the procedure of civil proceedings allows for a full determination of the damage caused to the victim. Because the recovery of expenses, actual damage, and lost profits incurred by the victim to restore their violated rights is also established by civil legislation. In the administrative-legal procedure, only the loss or damage of the victim's property (actual damage) is taken into account as damage. Thus, the Code of Administrative Offenses does not establish legal mechanisms for recovering from the offender expenses incurred by the victim to restore the violated right and lost profits (for example, lost income for sick days).

According to Article 38 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility, a person who has committed an administrative offense is obliged to compensate for the damage caused as a result of the administrative offense[5]. It is also provided that the decision to recover this damage in favor of the victim is made by the authorized body (official) during the application of punishment to the guilty party, that is, during the proceedings in the case of an administrative offense. Considering that, according to the current procedure, cases of administrative offenses are considered extrajudicially by more than 30 authorized state bodies (officials) and administrative penalties are applied, these authorized bodies, when considering a case of an administrative offense, must also determine whether property damage was caused to the victim (Article 307 of the Code of Administrative Offenses). However, although the Code of Administrative Offenses stipulates that

state bodies (officials) resolve the issue of compensation for damage caused to the victim as a result of administrative offenses, there are no norms defining how to recover damages from the offender. In other words, measures ensuring the recovery of the damage caused by the offender at his expense in favor of the victim are not clearly defined in any article of the code. This, in practice, often leads to the fact that the damage caused by the administrative offense is not compensated to the victim and the administrative offense case ends with the application of administrative penalties to the offender. As a result, citizens appeal to various state bodies to recover damages from offenses.

Indeed, we acknowledge that the main task in administrative offense proceedings is to strengthen legality, protect the interests of the individual, the state, and society, and establish fair liability for committed offenses. Nevertheless, when conducting an administrative offense case, the state body (official) considering the case is obliged to take all legal measures to compensate the victim for the damage caused. Among these measures, compensation for damage caused to the victim by the person who committed the administrative offense is taken into account as a circumstance mitigating responsibility when imposing punishment on him, the victim can apply to the civil court on the basis of the decision of the state body (official) that considered the administrative offense, and compensation for damage is resolved in accordance with civil law. However, if the legislation does not establish strict and specific measures for recovering damages caused by an administrative offense from the guilty party in favor of the victim, the aforementioned measures will not be sufficiently effective.

It should be noted that, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 20, 2015 No. 3PY-391, a separate Chapter XVII "Administrative Responsibility for Obstruction, Illegal Interference in the Activities of Entrepreneurs, and Other Offenses Violating the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Economic Entities," consisting of 11 articles, was introduced into the Code of Administrative Offenses. It should be noted that the introduced norms contribute to the free operation of entrepreneurs, the administrative and legal protection of their rights and freedoms. However, as noted above, these articles also do not provide for strict measures to recover damages caused to an entrepreneur as a result of an administrative offense. In our opinion, in order to more effectively protect the rights and interests of entrepreneurs, it is advisable to include the following methods of civil law protection in the content of these articles. These are:

firstly, the issue of exempting offenders from liability in case of voluntary compensation for damage caused to entrepreneurs;

secondly, the procedure for recovering expenses incurred or to be incurred by the entrepreneur to restore the violated right as a result of the offense, the loss or damage (actual damage) to his property, as well as lost income (lost profit), which the entrepreneur could have received under normal conditions of civil circulation if his rights had not been violated;

thirdly, the introduction of strict and specific measures ensuring the recovery of damages from the offender in favor of the entrepreneur;

Fourthly, provisions providing for criminal liability in relation to officials or civil servants in cases of repeated commission of the same offense within a year after the application of administrative penalties.

When considering the damage caused as a result of administrative offenses, it is also advisable to dwell on the need to determine the subject responsible for the damage or to whom the claim for compensation for damage should be addressed. Because, according to the general rule, the damage caused must be fully compensated by the person who caused it. However, there are cases when the legislation provides for the liability of third parties, more precisely, the state, for causing harm. For example, Part 1 of Article 302 of the Code of Administrative Offenses "Compensation for Damage Caused to a Citizen as a Result of Illegal Bringing to Administrative Responsibility" states: "Damage caused to a citizen as a result of illegal bringing to administrative responsibility is compensated by the state in full regardless of the fault of the body (official) that considered the case on the administrative offense." The same rule is established in the norms of civil law. For example, part 1 of Article 991 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Damage caused to a citizen as a result of unlawful conviction, unlawful prosecution, unlawful application of detention as a preventive measure or obtaining a receipt for decent behavior, unlawful imposition of an administrative penalty in the form of detention, as well as the use of any torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, shall be compensated by the state in full in the manner prescribed by law, regardless of the fault of officials of the bodies conducting the pre-investigation check, the inquiry, preliminary investigation, the prosecutor's office, and the court"[6]. However, there is no mechanism for the practical application of the legal norm provided for in the above article, which states that..."payment is made by the state in full in the manner prescribed by law." Also, the issue of which state body will compensate for the damage and in what

order is not defined. For these purposes, we consider it necessary to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Procedure for Payment of Monetary Payments from the State Budget," which defines the procedure for compensation for losses provided for in the above-mentioned articles of the Civil Code and the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Along with the above, when recovering damages caused by administrative offenses in favor of the victim, the body (official) considering the case must take into account a number of features. In this case, the subject who committed the administrative offense, the type of administrative offense, whether the property or personal interest damaged as a result of the administrative offense was insured or not are also important in solving the issue of compensation for damage caused as a result of the administrative offense. In particular, the following:

- the obligation of the state to compensate for damage caused as a result of certain administrative offenses committed by an official or civil servant (Article 302 of the Code of Administrative Offenses);

- property or material damage is not always caused as a result of any administrative offense (for example, as a result of an offense of insult or slander, the victim often suffers moral damage, and its compensation is protected by the court);

- insurance of property or personal interests damaged as a result of administrative offenses (for example, according to the law on compulsory insurance of civil liability of owners of vehicles, the insurance organization compensates the injured party for the damage), and these circumstances affect the resolution of the issue of compensation for damage during the proceedings in the case of an administrative offense.

Based on the foregoing, it should be emphasized that the issue of compensation for damages caused by administrative offenses must be finally resolved by the authorized state body (official) during the proceedings and consideration of the offense case, since the main task of law is not only to punish the offender, but also to restore violated rights.

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